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RNA-TARGETED THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES FOR VARIOUS DISEASES

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Abstract: RNA-based therapies have emerged as a very promising new avenue for treating various diseases. A number of RNA-targeting techniques are currently under investigation including antisense oligonucleotides, siRNA, aptamers, microRNAs and the powerful gene-editing tool CRISPR-Cas9. These strategies enable precise sequence-specific downregulation of expression of disease-causing genes or inhibition of RNA viruses at the post-transcriptional level. A number of RNA-targeting drugs have already been approved to treat neurological disorders like spinal muscular atrophy. Meanwhile, clinical trials are ongoing to evaluate their efficacy in oncology, cardiovascular diseases and genetic conditions like transthyretin amyloidosis, familial hypercholesterolemia and Huntington's disease. Several antisense drugs and RNAi therapeutics have also shown promising results against cancers in early to mid-stage clinical testing. Despite early success, significant research efforts are still ongoing to improve the stability, target affinity and specificity of nucleic acid therapeutics. Delivery remains a major challenge due to rapid degradation and difficulty in crossing biological membranes. Novel delivery technologies utilizing nanocarriers, peptides and polymers are being developed to protect RNA drugs and transport them efficiently across extracellular and intracellular barriers to achieve optimal therapeutic activity. RNA-based therapies represent a burgeoning field that holds tremendous potential for treatment of various hard-to-drug diseases. Further refinement of delivery systems is expected to realize their full clinical benefits in the years to come.

Keywords: RNA-based therapy, antisense oligonucleotide, siRNA, aptamer, microRNA, CRISPR-Cas9.

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DRUG DISCOVERY AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence is playing an increasingly important role in pharmaceutical research and development. Machine learning algorithms and deep neural networks are being applied at various stages from target identification to clinical trials. In early discovery, computational methods allow screening large molecular libraries in silico to predict potential drug candidates. Deep learning reviews chemical structures and their properties at scale, identifying compounds most likely to interact with biological targets of interest. This helps nominate fewer molecules for further testing in vitro and in vivo. AI tools also analyze vast gene expression, protein-protein interaction and epidemiological data to pinpoint novel disease pathways and drug targets. Complex algorithms uncover previously unknown patterns and associations within huge datasets. This facilitates target validation and mechanistic understanding. Machine learning predictive models study existing molecules to infer their absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity profiles without animal or human testing. Such computational toxicology helps avoid late-stage drug failures and costs. Furthermore, AI assists clinical trial optimization. It evaluates outcomes of past studies to design more efficient protocols. Algorithms also examine patient characteristics and response parameters to predict cohorts that may benefit or face risks. Such predictive analytics enable more targeted patient enrollment. Lastly, artificial intelligence studies data from all trials, published literature and post-marketing reports. This aids discovery of unknown adverse effects, identification of best responding patient subsets and maximizes real-world evidence for treatment optimization. Incorporation of AI at key points in R&D enhances productivity by reducing costs, accelerating development timelines and improving chances of success. The computational abilities of machine learning are transforming pharmaceutical research.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, drug discovery, clinical trials.

3D BIOPRINTING OF TISSUES FOR PRECLINICAL DRUG TESTING AND REGENERATIVE MEDICINE

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Abstract: Three-dimensional bioprinting is an emerging tissue engineering technique that holds tremendous potential for developing preclinical tissue models and individualized regenerative treatments. Through precise layer-by-layer deposition of live cells, biomaterials and growth factors, 3D bioprinters can fabricate tissues and organ constructs that closely mimic the native microstructure and architecture of organs. Researchers have successfully generated complex 3D printed tissue models of vital organs like liver, kidney, bone and skin. When exposed to drugs or toxicants, these bio-printed tissues exhibit responses similar to natural organs, making them highly useful replacements for conventional animal testing models in the preclinical drug development process. In addition, 3D bioprinting offers a promising approach for fabricating Replacements or repair solutions for damaged tissues and organs. By incorporating a patient's own cells combined with appropriate biomaterials into 3D printed constructs, this technology enables generation of personalized grafts customized for each individual. This helps avoid issues associated with limited organ availability and immune rejection. As bioprinting technologies continue to evolve, the ability to print full-scale organ constructs with vasculature is moving within reach. This could help address the dire shortage of organs available for transplant worldwide. 3D tissue bioprinting presents an innovative path towards both developing predictive preclinical models and advancing the field of individualized regenerative medicine.

Keywords: 3D bioprinting, tissue engineering, preclinical testing, regenerative medicine, organ-on-chip.

NANOTECHNOLOGY-BASED PLATFORMS FOR ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract: The field of nanotechnology is transforming drug delivery through the engineering of novel nanoscale carriers and systems. Nanocarriers constructed from materials such as polymers, lipids, albumin and inorganic nanoparticles have revolutionized the delivery of diverse therapeutics. Drugs encapsulated within or attached to these nano-platforms demonstrate substantially improved bioavailability, stability and controlled release profiles compared to conventional formulations. The miniature size of nanocarriers allows them to efficiently penetrate deep into target tissues and diseased sites. Additionally, some nanocarriers can be guided to specific pathological locations like tumors using magnetic targeting or active ligands conjugated to their surfaces. This enhances drug accumulation at sites of action and lowers systemic exposure, thereby improving efficacy and safety. Controlled release from stimuli-responsive nanocarriers ensures therapeutic payloads are maintained at therapeutic levels for extended periods, while simultaneously minimizes unwanted fluctuations in drug levels. Nanotechnology also enables co-delivery of multiple drug and gene payloads within one nanomedicine for complementary or synergistic therapies. Ongoing research is focused on developing versatile multifunctional nanoplateforms that combine passive and active targeting capabilities along with stimuli-triggered release. Such advanced nanocarriers show promise for delivery of different classes of drugs including peptides, proteins and nucleic acid therapeutics to further expand nanomedicine applications.

Keywords: Nanocarriers, drug delivery, controlled release, targeted delivery, stimuli-responsive.

3D PRINTING OF PERSONALIZED ORAL DRUG PRODUCTS

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Abstract: The emergence of 3D printing is opening new possibilities for personalized drug product design and on-demand manufacturing. This advanced additive manufacturing technique allows for precise fabrication of complex oral dosage forms such as tablets and capsules tailored to individual patient requirements. 3D printing enables incorporation of multiple active ingredients, incorporation of taste-masking agents, and development of optimized controlled-release profiles matching each patient's therapeutic needs. Complex geometries and variable dose strengths can be produced on demand. Many studies have focused on using food-grade 3D printers along with standardized pharmaceutical ingredients to generate personalized pills. Excipients like sugars can be selected to make the prints more palatable. Colorants and flavorants may also be added for easy administration to pediatric, geriatric patients or those with swallowing difficulties. Combining 3D printing with real-time analysis of patient-specific data and formulation optimization ensures maximum medication adherence and desired outcomes. Printing facilities located closer to patients could supply tailored medication on short notice, improving access and convenience. This personalized manufacturing approach has the potential to profoundly transform pharmacy services. It promises far superior treatment individualization compared to conventional production methods. With further refinement, 3D printed drugs may achieve more effective health outcomes on a wider population scale.

Keywords: 3D printing, personalized medicine, drug product design, controlled release, pediatric/geriatric formulations.

CHALLENGES AND APPLICATIONS OF BIOME THERAPEUTICS

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Abstract: Microbiome treatments employ additive, subtractive, or modulatory strategies to engineer the microorganisms. The goal of microbiome augmentation is to counteract the drawbacks of conventional drugs and offer more promising therapeutic treatment of human illnesses. The goal of microbiome therapies is to modify the gut microbiome by using bacteriophages, antibiotics, bacteriocins, native or synthetic bacteria, or subtractive or modulatory therapy. By offering individualized, harmonized, dependable, and long-lasting treatment, this strategy may be able to overcome the limitations of traditional therapies. Microbiome treatments have a lot of potential, but they are still in the early stages of development and have a lot of administrative and technological problems that need to be investigated. Human health is significantly influenced by the microbial population that resides on and within the human body, affecting everything from immunity to metabolism. The biomedical research community today faces the task of translating our understanding of the microbiome into effective Medicinal therapy. Manipulation of the intestinal microbiome has significant potential to lower the occurrence and/or severity of a wide range of human illnesses and diseases. An increasing amount of research on human microbiome correlations and molecular pathways in mouse models has brought attention to the crucial role that gut dysbiosis plays in the pathophysiology of food allergies. Therefore, new approaches to prevent and treat food allergies make sense when targeting the gut microbiota, and techniques to alter the gastrointestinal microbiome to counteract immunological dysregulation show promise for future clinical application.

Keywords: Gut microbiota, Microbiome modulation, Probiotics, Prebiotics, Bacteriotherapy, Food allergies.

IN-SILICO INVESTIGATION OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS FOR POTENTIAL ANTI-OXIDANT ACTIVITY

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Abstract: Computational drug discovery methods like network pharmacology and molecular docking can effectively aid the development of phytochemical-derived therapeutics. This study utilizes a network pharmacology approach integrated with molecular docking to determine key bioactive targets and potential pharmacological mechanisms of phytochemicals from medicinal plants. Network pharmacology employs a systematic pipeline to investigate therapeutic effects of phytochemicals at a system-level. It computationally elucidates molecular interactions between drugs and biological targets to enhance understanding of drug actions. This technology can also identify new chemical entities and repurpose existing drugs for wider therapeutic applications. Molecular docking simulates ligand-receptor conformations and atomic interactions, predicting affinity in silico. It is widely used for cost-effective drug discovery and pathway elucidation due to accuracy. In this study, network pharmacology identified putative phytochemical bioactives and targets. Molecular docking then validated target bindings and pharmacological mechanisms. This integrated computational strategy presents an effective virtual screening approach for phytochemical discovery.

Keywords: Phytochemicals, Network pharmacology, Molecular docking, Medicinal plants, Computational drug discovery.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES ON NANOTECHNOLOGY-BASED OCULAR DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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Abstract: Ocular barriers form challenges in ophthalmic drug delivery. The eye's complex anatomy and physiology presents both static and dynamic barriers that hinder the passage of exogenous compounds and therapeutic agents via topical administration. This review aims to provide insights into these barriers by first describing the structure of the eye and associated constraints. This is followed by an overview of common ocular diseases like glaucoma and their current clinical treatments, highlighting the importance of pharmaceutical intervention in managing ocular conditions. Recent advances, especially those employing nanotechnology-based ocular drug delivery systems, are then discussed. Several promising preclinical studies utilizing nano carriers are summarized with the goal of aiding future research. Specifically, we review nanotechnology-enabled ophthalmic formulations currently in preclinical or clinical trial stages as well as approved Nano carriers. In conclusion, based on current trends and therapeutic approaches, we provide perspectives on the challenges faced by novel ocular pharmaceutical delivery systems and further propose directions for future research. We believe this comprehensive review can serve to inform and stimulate further advancement and innovation in modern ophthalmic formulations. The review aims to facilitate a better understanding of ocular barriers and highlights the potential of nanotechnology to overcome these barriers.

Keywords: Ocular barriers, Glaucoma, Nanotechnology, Ocular drug delivery.

DEVELOPMENT OF HYDROGEL SYSTEM FOR TARGETED CANCER THERAPY

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Abstract: Hydrogel materials possessing enhanced biocompatibility and biodegradability show promise as novel drug carriers for cancer treatment. They provide three key advantages. Firstly, hydrogels can function as precise and controlled drug release systems. Widely used in cancer therapies like chemotherapy, radiotherapy, immunotherapy, hyperthermia, and photodynamic therapy, they enable continuous and systematic release of drugs for chemotherapy, radionuclides, immunosuppressants, hyperthermia agents and other substances. Secondly, hydrogels come in various sizes and can be delivered via different methods, allowing targeting of drugs to specific cancer sites and subtypes. This enhances medication targeting and reduces drug dosages needed, increasing treatment effectiveness. The ability of hydrogels to intelligently respond to internal and external stimuli enables remote-controlled and on-demand release of anti-cancer actives. Hydrogels combining these advantages show potential to improve cancer survival rates and patient quality of life. Hydrogels are fabricated from various polymers to deliver both synthetic and natural cytotoxic compounds in the tumor microenvironment, such as breast cancer tissue. Smart hydrogels release cytotoxic drugs at this site in response to stimuli like pH, temperature and light, extending drug duration of action locally. This tailored delivery and retention at the target location also helps mitigate side effects. The stimulus-triggered delivery of lethal agents to tumor microenvironments is generating interest in intelligent hydrogels for targeted cancer therapy.

Keywords: Hydrogel, Drug delivery, Cancer therapy, Targeted delivery, Stimuli-responsive.

THE RISE OF DIGITAL THERAPEUTICS AND THEIR POTENTIAL IN TRANSFORMING HEALTHCARE DELIVERY

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Abstract: Digital therapeutics (DTx) are evidence-based, software-based interventions to prevent, manage, or treat medical disorders and disease. They utilize digital or online health technologies to change patient behaviors and deliver therapeutic interventions. As a novel treatment approach based on digital technologies, DTx are gaining commercial adoption and clinical evidence, addressing the increasing demand for solutions in new clinical areas. Utilizing digital technologies within overburdened healthcare systems can enhance treatment outcomes and potentially replace some traditional care approaches. Regulatory agencies recognize DTx potential, with the U.S. FDA establishing the Digital Health Program to promote innovation, clarify policies for digital health technologies, and engage stakeholders. Digital therapies directly deliver clinically-validated therapeutic content to patients using software formats such as apps, games and virtual reality. They offer a new class of treatments compared to conventional options. Healthcare professionals must understand digital therapies to appropriately prescribe and encourage their use.

Keywords: Digital therapeutics, Digital health, Healthcare delivery, Software-based interventions, Regulatory policy.

AYAHUASCA: AN ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: Ayahuasca is a traditional psychotropic beverage extensively utilized by indigenous tribes of the Amazon basin primarily for spiritual and therapeutic purposes. This beverage is concocted by an admixture of the Banisteriopsis caapi vine and other plant species, notably those containing the psychoactive compound dimethyltryptamine (DMT), such as Psychotria viridis. The synergistic interaction between these plants enables the oral activity of DMT, which is otherwise inactivated by monoamine oxidase enzymes in the human digestive system. The use of ayahuasca extends beyond traditional applications; it is increasingly explored for its potential therapeutic benefits, including psychological healing and spiritual insight. Recent years have seen a rise in its popularity in non-indigenous contexts, particularly in South American countries like Peru and Brazil, where ayahuasca tourism has become a significant phenomenon. This globalization has sparked both interest and controversy, highlighting the need for rigorous ethnopharmacological studies to better understand its effects and implications..

Keywords: Ayahuasca, Banisteriopsis caapi, dimethyltryptamine (DMT), ethnobotany, psychedelic, therapeutic use, ayahuasca tourism.

E-POSTERS

In-silico Investigation of Phytoconstituents for Potential Anti-oxidant Activity

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Network Procedure

Constructed Network

Docking Procedure

3D- Structure

Computational drug discovery methods like network pharmacology and molecular docking can effectively aid the development of phytochemical-derived therapeutics.

Network pharmacology approach integrated with molecular docking is used to determine key bioactive targets and potential pharmacological mechanisms of phytochemicals from medicinal plants.

Network pharmacology employs a systematic pipeline to investigate therapeutic effects of phytochemicals at a system-level.

It computationally elucidates molecular interactions between drugs and biological targets to enhance understanding of drug actions.

This technology can also identify new chemical entities and repurpose existing drugs for wider therapeutic applications.

Molecular docking simulates ligand-receptor conformations and atomic interactions, predicting affinity *in silico*.

It is widely used for cost-effective drug discovery and pathway elucidation due to accuracy

AYAHUASCA: AN ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Ayahuasca is a psychedelic plant-based drink that has a long history of traditional use by indigenous Amazonian tribes in religious ceremonies and healing practices. Ethnobotanical research continues to highlight its spiritual and medicinal significance in these indigenous communities. The brew is prepared by combining the Banisteriopsis caapi vine with other plants containing dimethyltryptamine (DMT) such as Psychotria viridis, creating a potent psychoactive concoction. The commercialization and popularization of ayahuasca as a recreational therapy in countries such as Peru and Brazil has attracted tourists seeking psychedelic experiences.

INTRODUCTION

Ayahuasca is a naturally-occurring hallucinogen have been used for a period of 1000 years by many indigenous cultures, not only in religious and spiritual ceremonies but also due to their medicinal benefits. The rapid adoption in modern culture mainly due to their popularity as recreational drugs. Capacity of these compounds is to induce mood alterations, variations in a person's perception, mainly visual, and altered thought with overpowering intellectual or spiritual insight, similar to what is experiencing only through dreams or at times of holy promotion. Foremost part of this hallucinogen drug (meaning that the drug produces hallucinations) is to show psychedelic ("mind revealing"), a term that do not focus on one specific effect. Additionally, their use does not lead to dependence, nor they are consumed for long periods of time. Ayahuasca, a Quechua word that means "vine of the souls" and also known as yagé, hoasca, caapi, daimé and natem, is a hallucinogenic herbal preparation with long traditional use both for therapeutic and divination purposes by indigenous tribes of the Amazon Basin, who consider it a sacred beverages. It is classified into two main chemical families: (i) phenylalkylamines, such as the well-known mescaline obtained from the peyotecactus (Lophophora williamsii) and (ii) indolealkylamines that can be further divided into ergolines, like the semi synthetic lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), the simple tryptamines, including N,N-dimethyltryptamine (DMT) and the phosphorylated counterpart 4-phosphoryloxy-N,N-DMT. These psychedelics share a similar mode of action, acting as agonists (or partial agonists) of the serotonin (5-HT_{2A}) receptor 5-HT_{2A}, through which they exert their effects in the central nervous system (CNS).

CONCLUSION

In exploring the transformative nature of ayahuasca, which has many health benefits, we draw attention to the value of indigenous knowledge shared through traditional rituals and ceremonial practices. However, it is important to note that the effects of ayahuasca can vary widely from person to person and that more research is needed to fully understand the mind sets. Even more than this, it is important to approach the use of ayahuasca in conjunction with supportive practices, such as meditation it constituting of significant biological properties like depression, anxiety, PTSD, addiction disorders.

HEALTH BENEFITS:

- MOOD AND EMOTIONS
- DEPRESSION
- ANXIETY
- SUBSTANCE ABUSE
- EMOTIONAL MATURITY

ADVERSE EFFECT:

- INCREASED BLOOD PRESSURE
- NAUSEA
- VOMITING
- TREMORS
- HALLUCINATION

PREPARATION

It is made by soaking or boiling the stems of B.caapi (source of Harmine), a tropical vine of the order Malpighiales, with the leaves of the Chacruna plant (Psychotria viridis), Diplopterys cabrerana, Mimosa tenuiflora, among other ingredients which can vary greatly from one shaman to the next. The resulting brew may contain the powerful psychedelic drug dimethyltryptamine and monoamine oxidase inhibiting harmala alkaloids, which are necessary to make the DMT orally active by allowing it (DMT) to be processed by the liver.

Ayahuasca Preparations	DMT (mg/mL)	Harmine (mg/mL)	Harmaline (mg/mL)	THH (mg/mL)	Total Alkaloids (mg/mL)
Rio Purus	0.13	0.15	n.a	0.05	0.33
UDV	0.24	1.70	0.20	1.07	3.21
Pucallpa	0.60	4.67	0.41	1.60	7.28

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